

iGuide - A new way for discovering tourist hotspots with children

Rosamelia Parizotto-Ribeiro¹
rosamelia.parizotto@gmail.com

Carolina Baronio¹
carolina.baronio@gmail.com

Debora Janzen¹
debora_j94@hotmail.com

Ana Carolina Penteadó¹
anacarlina_penteadó@hotmail.com

¹*Federal University of Technology - Paraná, Brazil*

Abstract This paper describes the iGuide, a new device that will help families to have a pleasant and interesting tour in the city of Curitiba (Brazil), going from one attraction to another while having fun. The iGuide is in the shape of a magnifying glass that uses a hologram to show information about tourist hotspots, maps and important places that the family may need during the tour. The children will be the ones using the device and they are going to be the guides for their families. In this way they would not get bored or bother their parents during the tour. The device brought a new way of exploring the city.

Keywords *Conceptual product, Emotional design, Children, Tourism*

Introduction

Curitiba, the capital of Paraná, is a beautiful city for families to visit. Parks, museums and important monuments are a “must see”. The city hall has a sightseeing bus tour that, just like every tourist bus, takes the visitors from one attraction to another. Even though Curitiba is a big city, many tourist hotspots are very close to each other and it is possible to walk from one to another, instead of getting on the bus for just a short drive. That is why the iGuide was developed. The iGuide is a conceptual product, a magnifying glass that will help families to have an interesting tour that provides information about the tourist places without getting lost. The most interesting part of this system is that children will be responsible for handling it, becoming the guides of the tour.

Theoretical basis

The need to understand the emotional aspects presented in human interactions with products is essential in the field of design. In this sense, emotional design aims to identify and understand features related to the perception and cognition of the individual towards objects.

Objects are able to influence the occurrence of certain emotions, affecting the process of the design. As Desmet (In: SUSAGROUP, 2015) claims, emotions are part of human nature and everything in the world has a constant influence on them. Therefore, it is impossible to ignore the emotional side of product experience; it would be like denying that products are designed, bought and used by humans.

The emotional design theory (Norman, 2004) presents a model of design with three levels. These levels affect the relations that individuals have with objects, combining both cognition and emotions. The visceral

level is concerned with appearances and it is not culturally dependent. The behavioural level is to do with product usability. The reflective level considers the status given by the product. These three levels of design motivated Norman to state that “aesthetically beautiful objects enable you to work better”.

In the design process, it is also important to analyse those levels in order to have a design capable of reaching the users’ desires. Löbach (1976) argues that the industrial designer must meet the multiple needs and aspirations of users and user groups, in order to provide the product with the appropriate functions for each case.

Desmet and Hekkert (2007) claim that “the emerging interest in user-centred design has stimulated a shift of focus from the users’ behaviour and cognition to the users’ affective experience of (and involvement in) the human-product interaction”. The authors distinguish three components of a product experience: aesthetic pleasure, attribution of meaning and emotional response.

The aesthetic experience is considered to be the product’s capacity to delight the sensory modalities, related to the shape, the colours, the sounds and the touch. The experience of meaning is related to cognition and its processes such as interpretation, memory retrieval and associations, where people can assess the symbolic significance of products. At the emotional level, Desmet and Hekkert (2007) refer to the affective phenomena considered in emotion psychology about emotions, love and disgust, fear and desire etc. The emotions are functional, establishing the position towards certain people, objects, actions and ideas. The development of this conceptual project was based on these concepts.

Figures 1 and 2. Digital mock-up of the iGuide and a detail of the "Next" button.

Methodology

The literature review helped to structure the concept of the product and it was based on Löbach's (1976) four stages of product development, which are: problem analysis, problem solutions, evaluation of problem solutions and realization of problem solution. However, the last stage was not considered as the product was a digital mock-up. The device's creative name came from the Technique Methodology developed by Nöllke (2010) and it is called Brainwriting. It consists of collecting as many names as possible in a very quick way, without judging if they are good or not. This is a very interesting and effective way to choose a good name for a project or device.

The conceptual product

Aims

The main idea for the project was to develop a system to help tourists get from one attraction to another in Curitiba, without worrying about getting lost. The development of the project started with some references of the Van Gogh Museum in Amsterdam (Holland), where children have some assignments during a visit with their parents, so they do not get bored and still have fun. This system could be motivating if combined with the idea of tourism for families in Curitiba.

The product took the shape of a magnifying glass so that the children would have an interesting object in their hands. The interaction would make the children feel important while guiding their family to the right place. The iGuide was developed to stimulate a new and different way to tour Curitiba.

Physical construction

The magnifying glass was designed to be 32cm in

length, with a circumference of 15cm, 1.5cm thick, and it has a string to tie to onto the child's wrist or rest round their neck (Figures 1 and 2). This object was made of acrylic, since it is very likely that it could fall to the ground. The circumference was translucent because it changes colour according to the way the family is going. The colour would be green if the user was going in the right way, or red if the user was going the wrong way. This system would work by being integrated with a GPS.

Use and features

The user would get the device from the bus driver as soon as they enter a bus. The first hologram would appear showing the instructions (Figures 3 and 4).

The magnifying glass has the whole route planned out and is operated using a GPS system. In order to go from one main tourist attraction to another, it would show other places on the way that were near to each other, guiding the family in the right direction. Supposing the family started their tour at the Oscar Niemeyer Museum and they had already finished the visit, the child would press the "Next" button to see the next point they had to look for. In this case, it would be Rio Iguazu Square, which is easy to find, since it is very close to the museum. It would appear for only five seconds but, in case the child forgets or does not see it, it was possible to press the "Next" button again and the same hologram would be shown. They would walk until they found Rio Iguazu Square and when they were nearby, the green light that was already on (since they had started to walk) would start to blink, indicating that they were close. It was time for the child to get into action and point the magnifying glass at the attraction, as if he or she were taking a picture. If the device recognised the place it would stop blinking and show a small text with information about it, also as a hologram. The child could read the

Figures 3 and 4. Instruction screens and hologram of the map.

Figure 5. Route from Oscar Niemeyer Museum to Passeio Público.

information out loud, presenting the details to the parents, feeling like a real guide. When the family was ready and wanted to move on, the child would press the “Next” button and the hologram for the next point would appear.

The next tourist spot could be seen from the Square so there was no way to get lost and if the child started walking in the wrong direction the green light would turn red, meaning that it was better to go back. In case the family did not find the right street, the device was prepared to guide them to the right path. By pressing the “Map” button a map would appear as a hologram, indicating where the family was and where they had to go (the tourist attraction they were looking for). The indicator would move as the family walked, so it is very easy to get back on track. When they got to the right attraction, the hologram would disappear automatically.

They could use three different buttons if they had some other special needs during the trip, “Bus” (green), “Food” (red) and “Toilet” (yellow). If anyone needed any of those options, they would press the button and a map would appear showing where the nearest option was. When the family was ready they could turn it on again by pressing the “Next” button to see where they should go, or the “Map” button, to help them get back on the right path.

Figure 5 shows an infographic of the route from the Oscar Niemeyer Museum to Passeio Público. The route illustrates only a small part of the city but it could be extended to other tourist attractions.

Logo

The main concern for the “iGuide” brand’s logo was to create a visual symbolism that could transmit the curious ambiguity of the letter “i”. It was decided to use “iGuide” because of the fun that the word could involve: “Eye Guide” and “iGuide” have the same pronunciation. However, they have different meanings. Some of the alternatives for the logo are shown in Figure 6. The colours chosen recall the colours of the Brazilian flag, green, yellow, blue and white.

Framework of product experience

Based on the framework of product experience by Desmet and Hekkert (In: Green and Jordan, 2002), it was possible to allocate the design of the iGuide at the levels proposed.

The aesthetic experience was considered in the design to develop a product, in this case, a magnifying glass, able to delight the sensory modalities: an interesting object with the idea of bringing the concept of discovering the city, with colours that could change according to the way people made the choice for the tour. The interface would also provide an enjoyable way to interact by using aesthetic features.

The experience of meaning was related to the interpretation and associations, where people could assess the symbolic significance of products. In this sense, using the iGuide, the children would present the details to their parents, impersonating a real tour guide. The parents would also be glad to give their children the power to show them the information about the sightseeing spots.

At the emotional level, this interaction would provide both parents and children with a pleasant experience that could be remarkable in many ways, bringing emotions such as pleasure and joy. The children would believe that they were in charge and the parents would be glad that their children would also be enjoying the trip.

Considerations

Tourism in Curitiba is an excellent programme for families and checking out all the tourist hotspots could be more interesting and efficient with the iGuide, the magnifying glass that could help families to get from one place to another.

The idea and concept were innovative and could attract more people to take the tourist buses and could, in the future, be a possibility for creating a new form of tourism for the city. The families could have a better experience discovering Curitiba in a different way. The project could inspire other kinds of devices

Figure 6. Alternatives for the logo.

or objects for tourists to explore the beauty of the city of Curitiba and other cities as well.

This project was carried out during a Conceptual Design course. This was part of the internationalisation process of the Federal University of Technology – Parana. It was offered in English and the students were from the Design course. They were not concerned with technical and economic issues so it gave them a great deal of freedom to create an interactive product where the emotions played a bigger role during the development process than the usual process. This approach was able to embrace new ways of interpreting and developing design.

References

Desmet, P and Hekkert, P. (2007). Framework of Product Experience. *International Journal of Design*, 1(1) 2007.

Green, W. and Jordan, P. (2002), *Pleasure with Products, beyond usability* (60 – 68) London: Taylor e Francis.

Löbach, B. (1976). *Design Industrial: bases para a configuração dos produtos industriais*. Rio de Janeiro: Edgar Blücher,

Leuder, R. and Rice, V.J.B. (2008). *Ergonomics for Children: Designing products and places for toddler to teens*. N.Y: Taylor & Francis.

Nöllke, M.(2010). *Kreativitätstechniken*. Germany: Haufe - Lexware, 6^o. edition.

Norman, D.A. (2004). *Emotional Design: Why we love (or hate) everyday things*. New York, NY: Basic Books.

SusaGroup. *About SusaGroup*. Retrieved 26 October 2015, from: <http://www.susagroup.com>